

DARIAH-EU

Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

2020

ANNUAL REPORT

The background features several thick, curved lines in shades of pink, red, orange, and yellow, arranged in a roughly circular pattern. Each line is terminated by a small white circle. The lines vary in length and curvature, creating a dynamic, abstract composition.

DARIAH ERIC:
A research infrastructure
to enhance and support
digitally enabled research
and teaching across the
Arts and Humanities.

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Foreword

As we finalise the DARIAH Annual Report for 2020, and look back at the activities of the year, the word that comes most prominently to mind is resilience. Throughout an exceptionally difficult period, the DARIAH ERIC has not only managed to continue its core activities in the face of adversity, but also to reinvent some of the fundamentals of its work, all in the service of our community and mission. This success is a testament not only to our agile organisational model and proximity to the real needs of our community, but also most assuredly to our staff and network of contributors, both in the central offices and across our 20 national nodes, projects and collaborators.

Our Annual Event was delayed and ultimately moved to a virtual format. Although our Croatian ‘hosts’ did a fabulous job of creatively and engagingly helping us to experience the rich sense of place they had imagined, our pleasure at the event was tinged with longing for all of the people, experiences and interactions we missed.

But for all the things that the COVID 19 pandemic took from us, it also gave us opportunities to explore new interpretations of the contribution DARIAH could make to its users. Open Science became an enabler and support we could promote to researchers facing unprecedented challenges. DARIAH has shown agility and resilience during the crisis and we demonstrated to our funders and member countries that humanities research is open research by default and a source of inspiration for others to tackle interdisciplinary challenges. Our experience of planning and hosting virtual events allowed us to set an example for colleagues struggling with the transition. And our biannual theme funding call for small, topical projects was able to expand to include not only a focus on the arts research within our community, but also on responses to the COVID crisis.

Many of our achievements in the year may seem quotidian on the surface, but in fact demonstrate not just resilience, but solidity, in the organisation. The year 2020 also saw us gather our first round of Balanced Scorecard data to evidence our impact (and sharpen our awareness of it). The last element in this suite of measures to which we have committed appears within this Annual Report, in the form of our first three qualitative case studies.

We bid our thanks to the founding Chairs of both our General Assembly and our Scientific Board, and welcomed active members of each of those bodies as they stepped into the vacancies. We welcomed our long-established partners in Switzerland as they officially joined DARIAH as our first Observers. We saw new projects be funded, and the results of our existing projects, such as SSHOC, come to tantalising maturity. We answered surveys and released position papers – all in a day’s work for DARIAH, but also an essential mechanism by which we achieve our goal to represent the interests of our community in wider infrastructural discussions.

As this Annual Report attests, even on the rocky soil of 2020, DARIAH has found ways to bloom and grow.

Jennifer Edmond
President of the Board of Directors

Chris De Loof
Chair of the General Assembly

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Chris De Loof'.

DARIAH in a Nutshell

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) enhances and supports digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. DARIAH is a research infrastructure bringing together people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure that sustains researchers in building, analysing and interpreting digital resources. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level, enabling the transition to Open Science, and beyond to Open Innovation. It preserves, provides access to, and disseminates research that stems from these collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed.

DARIAH's mission is to empower research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge about culture and society. We work towards developing an infrastructure that supports researchers working in the diverse community of practice known as the arts and humanities to build, analyse and interpret digital or hybrid resources. DARIAH was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in August 2014. In 2020, the consortium had 19 Members, 1 Observer and 27 Cooperating Partners across 9 non-member countries.

DARIAH's Response to COVID 19

In these unprecedented times, DARIAH continued to support its research communities even more strongly by:

- moving all operations virtually, coordinating work remotely, providing virtual tools for its communities to meet and offering expertise, e.g. best practices in organising online events, and Open Access tools for online teaching
- transforming all planned events to online formats with the most important being the DARIAH Annual Event 2020. Over the course of the year, DARIAH planned and successfully organised a large number of online events and meetings, also on behalf of its project partners
- launching the DARIAH Theme Funding Call on the challenges of COVID 19 from an arts and humanities perspective

Activity Highlights 2020

1 Launch of #TrainingTuesday Twitter Campaign

The year 2020 started with the launch of #TrainingTuesday, a weekly Twitter campaign that aimed to bring learning resources and training videos, hosted on DARIAH-Campus or developed by DARIAH-affiliated projects, to researchers and course-providers within the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. More than 45 training resources were highlighted on Tuesdays throughout 2020 with 2469 total engagements on Twitter. (See page 28).

1

January

3 DARIAH Virtual Exchange Session

In light of the decision to postpone the DARIAH Annual Event 2020, initially planned to take place in Zagreb, Croatia in May, DARIAH organised an online exhibition of resources and ideas exploring the many primitives of and issues surrounding scholarly meetings. The exhibition culminated in a 2-hour synchronous virtual exchange session on May 28 that brought together approximately 80 participants from all over the world. (See page 22).

3

May

2 New DARIAH Working Group on Research Data Management

In April, DARIAH welcomed a new Working Group on Research Data Management that aims to fulfill DARIAH's mission of facilitating access to data and supporting the DARIAH communities, through training and advocacy work, in adopting research data management best practices and methods. The Working Group currently has 37 members from all over Europe. (See page 11).

2

April

4 Alpha Release of the SSH Open Marketplace

On July 3, 25 representatives of the DARIAH community joined the 'SSH Open Marketplace Public Consultation' event to get an early glimpse of the alpha release of the SSH Open Marketplace and to share their feedback. The alpha release was only open to testers and the project community. The SSH Open Marketplace is a discovery portal connected to the EOSC ecosystem which is developed within the SSHOC project, funded by the European Commission. (See page 26).

4

July

DARIAH Theme Funding Call

In 2020, we launched the fifth edition of the bi-annual DARIAH Theme Call dedicated to 'Arts Exchanges' and 'Arts, Humanities and COVID 19'. This call targeted arts practitioners, DH researchers and DARIAH partner institutions to embark on collaborative projects and explore, on the one hand, the infrastructural requirements of the arts community with regards to the technologies they use, and seek, on the other hand, specific responses to the pandemic that engage arts and humanities sources, approaches and insight. (See page 24).

5

September

Launch of DARIAH In-House Webinar Series 'Friday Frontiers'

In October, DARIAH launched a series of In-House Webinars for the DARIAH community, called 'Friday Frontiers'. As a learning organisation, DARIAH offered its key staff and members a series of presentations and lectures on a variety of topics relevant to issues in the Digital Humanities. The first three webinars took place in Autumn/Winter 2020 on the topics of 'Post-Publication Peer Review', 'The Time Machine project' and 'Flipped Classrooms'. (See page 28).

6

October

Virtual Annual Event 2020: Scholarly Primitives

Taking place fully online from October 7 to December 2, this year's Annual Event had a different format than usual. The rich programme consisted of 15 weekly sessions of DARIAH Working Group meetings, synergy sessions and workshops, while the main week of the event in November hosted 18 paper presentations, a poster exhibition, one keynote and two social events. The Annual Event brought together more than 300 registered participants from 40 countries. (See page 23).

7

University of Princeton Joins DARIAH as First non-European Cooperating Partner

At its meeting in November, the DARIAH General Assembly approved the application of Princeton University (USA) to become DARIAH's first non-European Cooperating Partner. The Center for Digital Humanities (CDH) at Princeton University is one of the leading digital humanities research centers in North America. The partnership with DARIAH represents a great opportunity to expand the CDH's network of partnerships to the European audience. (See page 10).

8

November

1. Nurturing and Expanding DARIAH's Network

a. DARIAH at the National Level

The richness and dynamism of the DARIAH consortium lies first and foremost in the diversity and plurality of its member countries. It is they who every day through their actions, projects and influence make DARIAH a key infrastructure in the field of the arts and humanities. DARIAH's member countries meet and work through the National Coordinators Committee (NCC), which gathers regularly to reflect on and coordinate the actions of their national networks. In 2020, National Coordinators instituted a new, regular programme

of bi-monthly meetings to increase knowledge exchange and coordination.

Though at different stages in the construction of their national consortia, Switzerland and Portugal achieved a lot in 2020, a particularly challenging year. Their stories are featured below. We are also proud to feature some of the accomplishments of our members over the year, which you can find in the next pages.

Focus on Switzerland

Prof. Dr. Lukas Rosenthaler is the director of the Swiss Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) and the National Coordinator for Switzerland. He is assisted by Dr. phil. Vera Chiquet, who works at the DaSCH as Lukas's Deputy National Coordinator. DaSCH, founded last year, is the culmination of over ten years of work. Funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, DaSCH operates a platform for humanities research data that ensures long-term access to these data. Additionally, the DaSCH promotes linking of data with other databases, making research sustainable and reusable.

DaSCH. Some of these projects are ongoing, some are future projects, but overall it shows the interest for what we are doing across Switzerland.

Could you introduce us to the role and work of your consortium?

My task involves coordinating the DaSCH towards DARIAH and other international organisations, but also towards our national and regional partners. We also disseminate information, be they best practices, funding calls, or opportunities for collaboration. We enable on the one hand our researchers to become part of the DARIAH network, offering our own expertise, services, and tools, and on the other hand, we transfer these experiences and knowledge back to Switzerland. It really goes in two directions, we serve as an interface to both sides.

What would you consider the 2020 highlights of DARIAH-CH?

I'd say our biggest highlight is that we exist! It's always a big step to start a research infrastructure, and we grew the DaSCH office from 4 staff members to over 20, and this during the Coronavirus pandemic. We also secured funding from the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), giving us long term sustainability. Finally, in terms of our "birth," we worked with the SNSF and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation to make an application to the DARIAH General Assembly in November as an Observer, where we were unanimously approved.

Our main mission is to ensure that qualitative research data in the humanities is stored and maintained in such a way that it's available for future use and consultation. There is a real need to keep these databases available for the future beyond the funding life of the project that produced them. With multiple different styles of databases and multiple versions of each, it would be very difficult if not impossible to maintain all these different databases in the long term. Therefore, we constructed a common infrastructure where we can emulate these different data models into one infrastructure. Once they are put into our system, we only need to keep one database maintained, rather than multiple. Part of this mission is also to have materials available for projects early on and to inform them of best practices, as it makes our task easier down the road.

In terms of education, we have had multiple activities in BA, MA and PhD levels. There was even a Doctoral Day in the Digital Humanities, where we introduced DARIAH and the DH network in Switzerland to a new generation of scholars.

DaSCH members participated in multiple conferences as well, including the DARIAH Annual Event on Scholarly Primitives. Claire Clivaz also organised a conference on VREs (Virtual Research Environments) and Ancient Manuscripts in the fall.

We're looking forward to continuing establishing ourselves in Switzerland in the coming year.

Lukas Rosenthaler

Vera Chiquet

Focus on Portugal

Dr. Amélia Aguiar de Andrade is a Full Professor in the Department of History at the Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Director of the Biblioteca Mário Sottomayor Cardia e dos Centros de Documentação, and National Coordinator for Portugal. A Medieval historian who works on urban spaces, Amélia has over twenty years of experience working with European projects. Since 2017, she is the project lead for the ROSSIO infrastructure in Portugal. Portugal joined DARIAH as a member in 2016.

Could you introduce us to the role and work of your consortium?

Named after the famous square and meeting place in Lisbon, ROSSIO began as a consortium in 2013, building on the close cooperation between faculty members and cultural heritage professionals, and obtained funding from 2017 to develop and implement this infrastructure. It is led by the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences at the Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, and includes the Municipal Archives of Lisbon, the Cinemateca Portuguesa – National Museum of Cinema, the Portuguese Directorate-General for Books, Archives, and Libraries, the Scientific Computing Unit (FCCN) of Arquivo.pt, the Portuguese Directorate-General for Cultural Heritage, the National Theatre D. Maria II, as well as the Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation, a private foundation.

There is an incredible diversity of materials in our portal, with materials from museums, theatres, and archives across Portugal. We have over 30 million digital objects from the National Archives alone, which include documents related to the Portuguese administration of its former colonies. It is really important for us to make this content, which is physically available in Portugal, available in Open Access to people all around the world.

The ROSSIO portal has three main pillars: First, there is a virtual research environment for researchers and interested members of the public for interacting with the digital cultural heritage collections. Secondly, there are training materials, including MOOCs on Portuguese culture and history. Finally, there are online exhibitions and collections, for the general public. Indeed, we want to extend our reach not just to professors and teachers across Portugal, but also to professionals in the tourism industry, so that they have access to high quality materials. It is part of our even broader mission to make sure that knowledge produced and held in the universities is made available to the general public.

What would you consider the 2020 highlights of DARIAH-PT?

Despite the coronavirus pandemic, 2020 was still a year where we accomplished a great deal. This past year was primarily a time to focus on the development of the ROSSIO platform. This internal work was a vital step towards our 2021 goals for publicising the portal.

We also started the development of a thesaurus on the arts, humanities and social sciences. This thesaurus, which will be published in Open Access, is important for explaining the work of the portal to the greater public. We also began to develop several different MOOCs in collaboration with the NAU Platform, a technical infrastructure for publishing and course tracking in Portugal.

Dr. Amélia Aguiar de Andrade

Portugal, Image by Frank Nürnberger from Pixabay

2020 Highlights from our Members

Greece

Organisation of the Twitter Conference “DH in the Time of Virus” in April 2020, the first Greek-run international Digital Humanities conference which took place entirely on Twitter, as a response to the COVID 19 pandemic. The conference, which was organised in the context of APOLLONIS, the Greek Infrastructure for Digital Arts, Humanities and Language Research and Innovation, led to more than 2.8K user interactions and conversations from all over the world.

Poland

A success story comes from Poland as in November 2020 the “DARIAH-PL – Digital Research Infrastructure for Humanities and the Arts” project was awarded funding of 99.800.000 PLN, approximately 22,000,000 €, in the context of the Smart Growth Operational Programme. This large-scale national project aims to build the Polish e-infrastructure for the arts and humanities with a consortium of 16 institutions led by the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center. DARIAH-PL is one of 70 Polish infrastructures placed in the [Polish Roadmap for Research Infrastructures](#).

Ireland

A new funding scheme ‘UK-Ireland Collaboration in the Digital Humanities’ was launched which aims to explore complementary strengths in the Digital Humanities between world-leading centres of excellence in the UK and Ireland, leading to new partnerships and cross-disciplinary projects. A number of introductory workshops were organised in 2020 in which DARIAH was presented as an established EU model of cross-disciplinary collaborations.

France

France launched a programme with regional partners (such as Réseau des Maisons des Sciences de l’Homme) for better collaboration and knowledge exchange on different initiatives nationally and in Europe in the areas of humanities and data management.

Italy

Implementation of the DARIAH-IT infrastructural project “Developing nAtional and Regional Infrastructural nodes of dAriaH in ITaly”, funded already in 2019 by the Ministry of Public Education (MIUR). The project is devoted to the enhancement of the technological component of the infrastructure through six data centers located in Central and Southern regions of Italy.

Slovenia

Organisation of the Virtual Conference on Language Technology and Digital Humanities in September 2020 by DARIAH-SI and CLARIN-SI with a rich programme of 30 paper presentations from Slovenia and beyond.

Austria

The national research infrastructure project DiTAH (Digitale Transformation der österreichischen Geisteswissenschaften/Digital transformation of Austrian Humanities), started in April 2020 with most of the current CLARIAH-AT partners and 2,000,000 € project funding awarded by BMBWF for a 3-year period.

Netherlands

In 2020, our partners in the Netherlands were busy preparing the CLARIAH++ (C++) 2021 bid while also drafting an integrated CLARIAH-NL roadmap in order to bring the various domains of the national infrastructure together.

Czech Republic

- Digital libraries involved in LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ opened up access to their content, numbering approx. 100 millions of digitised pages, for students and researchers during the COVID 19 pandemic restrictions, as on-site services of libraries were closed.
- New features were introduced in the development of the [Internet Language Reference Book \(ILRB\)](#) by partners of the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ consortium, a tool that aims to help the general public to use the Czech language correctly, from pronunciation to morphology and syntax. The popularity of the ILRB is growing steadily, and its internet portal is expected to reach over 20 million hits in 2020.

Belgium

- The [Flemish Research Infrastructures Roadmap](#) was published in June 2020 with the aim of providing a comprehensive overview of the existing and new international Research Infrastructures in Flanders, which the Flemish government has invested on since 2011, including DARIAH-BE.
- The CLARIAH-VL: Advancing the Open Humanities Service Infrastructure phase two project has been funded with 3,435,802 € for the 3-year period 2021-2024.

Germany

In 2020, Germany worked extensively with DARIAH-EU in the context of the [SSHOC project](#) in Work Package 7 "Creating the SSH Open Marketplace" and in Work Package 3 "Lifting Technologies and Services into the SSH Cloud". Examples of such tasks were the Switchboard integration (TextGrid Repository, DARIAH Repository, DraCor) and integration of new DARIAH tools into the Switchboard (DARIAH GeoBrowser, Annotate, Voyant, Topics Explorer), planning of outreach activities for the SSH Open Marketplace and organisation of workshops, such as the FAIR Research Data Management in SSH in Göttingen, Germany in January 2020.

Bulgaria

Bulgaria launched large-scale activities on the linguistic and semantic annotation of historical sources and secondary literature concerning 19th century Bulgarian, Ottoman and Balkan history. This was achieved via workspaces for tools such as INCePTION annotation and CLaRK XML encoding hosted on the infrastructure's servers. On top of that, Bulgaria organised a series of training events for humanities scholars to work on [CLaDA's platform](#) (National Interdisciplinary Research E-Infrastructure for Bulgarian Language and Culture).

Croatia

DARIAH-HR was awarded national funding by the Ministry of Science and Education for the period of 2020 – 2024. This led to the formation of a DARIAH-HR Coordination Office with two new assistants.

b. Cooperating Partners

New Strategy to Valorize the Relation Between DARIAH and its Cooperating Partners

In 2020, DARIAH reviewed its strategy towards Cooperating Partners and set up an organisational framework, formalised by a new application form and a binding agreement, establishing a new basis for this collaboration. The main objective of the new approach is to better engage Cooperating Partners with DARIAH, to support them more intensively to form a national consortium and to encourage the move to full DARIAH membership.

The following key actions are now part of the work plan of every 3-year-membership:

- Active participation in DARIAH bodies and initiatives
- Hosting a 'DARIAH Day' in the country of the Cooperating Partner
- Organisation of at least one face-to-face meeting between DARIAH representatives and the relevant ministry/funding agency to discuss potential membership

This new framework has been officially adopted by the DARIAH General Assembly in November and two new institutions have joined DARIAH as Cooperation Partners according to the new strategy: Princeton University (USA) and Eötvös Loránd University (Hungary).

Princeton University – DARIAH's first non-European Cooperating Partner

As one of the leading digital humanities research centers in North America, the Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton University is an interdisciplinary research center that sits at the intersection of the humanities, data science, and computer science.

The expected benefit in collaborating with DARIAH is primarily the opportunity to expand the CDH's network of partnerships to the EU audience, and thus integrate their work into a broader sphere of collaborative research infrastructures. More concretely, DARIAH and CDH plan to co-brand the 2021 workshop series "New Languages for NLP: Building Linguistic Diversity in the Digital Humanities" and to publish the resulting course training material on DARIAH-Campus.

DH_Budapest Conference 2018, organised in collaboration with DARIAH, CLARIN and Michael Culture Association

"We look forward to sharing CDH's strengths – our experience building large-scale DH projects, our expertise in DH software development and UX design, and our best practices in DH project management and collaborative research – with our European colleagues, and we look forward to learning from them", said Natalia Ermolaev, CDH Associate Director.

Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE) – Hungary's oldest university

The Centre for Digital Humanities at Eötvös Loránd University is the first Digital Humanities Department in Hungary and was established in September 2020 with the launch of a mandatory coursework for humanities students over a variety of programmes. The department pursues research interests in the development of semantic databases, prosopographic data networks, semantic technology (Linked open data), digital philology (TEI XML), Natural Language Processing, the creation of annotated literary corpora and stylometry.

As a result of the collaboration with DARIAH, ELTE aims to develop teaching and research activities in an international network, therefore enabling students and scholars to learn and work in a wider context of DH research.

ELTE will continue its participation in the DARIAH Working group 'DH Course Registry' with the objective of representing Hungarian DH-related education in the registry. Their involvement in the Working Group 'Research Data Management' is an excellent opportunity to align data publishing activities and repository development with guidelines defined by DARIAH.

Finally, with the support of DARIAH, ELTE expects to strengthen the impact of the Digital Heritage Lab, a national consortium led by ELTE which includes the University of Miskolc, the Hungarian National Archive and the Research Centre of the Humanities. This consortium could be the basis for developing a roadmap for full membership of Hungary in DARIAH.

Working Groups Activities: 2020 at a glance

c. Working Groups

DARIAH in 2020 counts 23 Working Groups (WGs). These are a good reflection of the diverse and rich landscape of the interdisciplinary research carried on in the arts and humanities, and in particular within the DARIAH infrastructure. As one of its strategic pillars, DARIAH is actively engaged in the support and growth of such a rich community of researchers.

In terms of the support, in 2020 the DARIAH Coordination Office established a workflow and agreement with Hypotheses for providing WGs with their own, DARIAH

branded, research blogs. This initiative aimed in supporting the communication of the WGs, within and beyond the DARIAH network, and encouraging regular dissemination of their work outputs by providing such channels and opportunities.

Aiming for better communication and dissemination of WGs work and outcomes, in 2020, on the occasion of the virtual format of the DARIAH Annual Event, the WG meetings opened up to external participants, welcoming non-members to follow the meetings and explore potential collaborations.

Focus on the New Working Group on Research Data Management

2020 saw the start of a new Working Group: the Research Data Management WG, chaired by Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra (DARIAH's Open Science Officer) and Marta Błaszczczyńska (Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences). The WG will bring together DARIAH's significant expertise in this space, offering a platform for knowledge exchange and promotion of best practice. In its first year, the WG already counts 37 members from across the DARIAH countries.

"We will showcase how different disciplinary communities can take advantage of open scholarly infrastructure and tools that are available for the DARIAH communities" explained Marta, co-chair of the RDM WG. "We will produce training and advocacy materials that show sensitivity to research practices and data support needs in the arts and humanities".

"It is hard to find a better environment for this initiative than the DARIAH community", added Erzsébet. "DARIAH is a unique meeting point for scholars, GLAM professionals and data practitioners who represent a wide range of disciplines, research interests, geographical and cultural backgrounds."

Marta Błaszczczyńska

Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra

i. A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

Advancing the State of the Art: DARIAH Working Group Lexical Resources

What is the activity?

The DARIAH Working Group Lexical Resources brings together experts working on tools and methods for the creation and dissemination of lexical resources. In addition to functioning as a forum for scholarly exchange and organising training activities, the WG leads the development of TEI Lex-0, a technical specification and a set of community-based recommendations for encoding machine-readable dictionaries.

What kind of impact does it have?

The work of the WG fosters research excellence through the creation and diffusion of new knowledge, the imparting of new skills and the development of new technical standards, while promoting scholarly networks and close collaboration across institutional and national borders.

Who benefits?

Lexicographers, linguists, humanities researchers, data modeling experts, especially those interested in standards and interoperability.

Rationale for and Overview of the Activity

Dictionaries lie at the core of humanity's ability to conceptualise, systematise and convey meaning. Indeed, a dictionary is many things at once: it is a text, a tool, a model of language, and a cultural artifact deeply embedded in the historical moment of its production [1]. The DARIAH Working Group Lexical Resources has been established to help scholars create, transform and study dictionaries as digital objects.

The activities of the DWGLR have been seminal in integrating and sustaining previous work on encoding dictionaries; improving the coverage of lexicographic data in the TEI Guidelines; propelling the scholarly debate around modeling lexicographic data; championing the importance of open standards to a new generation of scholars; and establishing TEI Lex-0 as an internationally recognised data interchange format. In recognition of these activities, the WG was awarded the 2020 Rahtz Prize for TEI Ingenuity by the TEI Consortium.

Description of the Impact

1. Integrating and Sustaining Previous Work

The need for a stricter customisation of the TEI standard aimed specifically at encoding lexical resources was established during the COST Action European Network of e-Lexicography (ENEL) in the period from 2013-2017 [2]. Upon the completion of the Action, the WG took it upon itself to implement TEI Lex-0 as an open-source project on GitHub [3] and make it available for easy online consultation [4].

The distributed, bottom-up model of a DARIAH Working Group proved itself to be flexible enough to attract wide community participation [5] while providing institutional stability necessary for a standardisation project of this magnitude.

2. Improving the Coverage of Lexicographic Data in TEI

In addition to creating the customised, examples-rich TEI Lex-0 Guidelines, which lexicographers, researchers and students can use to learn more about the best practices for encoding lexical data, the WG has contributed to the development of TEI itself by improving the handling of lexicographic data in the TEI Guidelines via a number of proposals which were subsequently accepted by the TEI Council [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12].

"Members of the DARIAH Working Group Lexical Resources have made a valuable contribution to the Dictionaries Chapter of the TEI Guidelines. Their efforts and their expertise have been formidable and highly appreciated by the TEI community over the years."

Martina Scholger, Chair, TEI Technical Council

3. Propelling the Scholarly Debate Around Modeling Lexicographic Data

Members of the WG have presented at a number of conferences and published a number of papers, not only on the rationale and the overall features of TEI Lex-0 [13], but also on a range of specific lexicographic

topics such as the encoding of written and spoken forms [14], etymologies [15], multiword expressions [16], usage labels [17], the challenges of encoding complex academic dictionaries [18] etc. This wide range of topics is indicative not only of the robustness of TEI Lex-0 itself, which can be used to describe all the elements of the dictionary macro-, micro- and mesostructure, but also of the contribution which members of the WG are making to the wider scholarly debate around modelling lexicographic data. For a full bibliography, see the TEI Lex-0 Zotero Group [19].

4. *Championing the Importance of Open Standards to a New Generation of Scholars*

TEI Lex-0 and best practices in lexical data modeling have been introduced to more than 90 young scholars from across Europe at a number of training events including: Lexical Data Masterclasses (Berlin, 2017 and 2018) [20, 21, 22, 23]; courses at the Lisbon Summer School in Linguistics (2018 and 2019) [24, 25] and a DH Training Workshop: Digital Methods for Linguistic Investigation (Berlin, 2019) [26].

“Participating in the Lexical Data Masterclass 2018 was a fascinating experience: I learned about the principles of TEI Lex-0 and how to work efficiently with XML editors. Perhaps most importantly, I got a chance to consult with experts from the DARIAH Working Group Lexical Resources on my own dictionary project. These exchanges proved to be especially valuable now that I’m writing my PhD thesis. Looking back, I realize how much this intense learning experience shaped my path as a young researcher.”

Marija Žarković, PhD Student at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

5. *Establishing TEI Lex-0 as an Internationally-Recognised Data Interchange Format*

TEI Lex-0 has been recognised as an interchange format (together with Ontolex-Lemon) of the European Lexicographic Infrastructure (ELEXIS) [27], which currently has 17 partner and 50 observer institutions from 35 countries. The ELEXIS Observers Network is constantly growing, and so will the global outreach of TEI Lex-0.

In addition, TEI Lex-0 has been chosen as the native encoding format in two recently funded projects: Electronic lexical database of Indo-Iranian languages funded by The Technology Agency of the Czech Republic [28]; and MORDigital: The Digitization of the Dicionario da Lingua Portuguesa by António de Morais Silva funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology [29].

“We chose TEI Lex-0 for our new project MORDigital because we wanted to use a standard, well-documented and interoperable format for encoding Dicionario da Lingua Portuguesa. We hold in high regard the consistency of TEI Lex-0 as well as the opportunity to engage directly with colleagues from the DARIAH Working Group Lexical Resources.”

Prof. Rute Costa, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa

6. *The Lexical Resources Working Group Wins the 2020 Rahtz Prize for TEI Ingenuity*

In recognition of the international impact that TEI Lex-0 has had on the modeling of lexicographic data, the DWGLR was awarded the 2020 Rahtz Prize for TEI Ingenuity, which is awarded to an individual or team judged to have made a significant contribution to the TEI Consortium’s mission of “developing and maintaining a set of high-quality guidelines for the encoding of humanities texts” [30].

d. Projects and Collaborations

i. New Transnational Open Science Collaboration

The COVID 19 pandemic changed the ways we think about Open Science and advocacy. On the one hand, the full remote working conditions in which we suddenly found ourselves showcased the utmost importance of unrestricted access to scientific and scholarly outcomes for researchers. On the other hand, it also changed the ways training around open research practices had been implemented in the manifold research contexts.

To study and improve the efficiency of novel Open Science training practices that have been developed in response to the COVID 19 crisis, DARIAH teamed up with a global and diverse assembly of Open Science training organisations and communities with strong commitment to Open Research Culture and Infrastructure, including [FSCI](#), [The Carpentries](#), [European Open Science Cloud Synergy](#) project, [Australian Research Data Commons](#), or [ORCID](#). In 2020, DARIAH also started a new partnership and research project called Reimagining Educational Practices for Open (REPO), funded by the prestigious [Alfred P. Sloan Foundation](#)-funded initiative.

This project will be working on capturing experiences of transitioning OS activities to an online virtual environment, in response to the COVID crisis, creating resources on Open Science training both virtually and in a post-COVID world and establishing new collaborations with organisations interested in “training for Open”.

Image by Guy Stevens on Unsplash

ii. Two Successful Project Funding Applications in 2020: CLS INFRA and EOSC Future

DARIAH successfully applied and received funding for two project proposals in 2020, in the context of the European Horizon 2020 programme: the Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA) and the European Open Science Cloud Future (EOSC Future) projects.

CLS INFRA is funded with approximately 5.000.000 € for a period of 4 years (2021-2025) to create a sustainable infrastructure to benefit the Computational Literary Studies research community. The main objective of the project is to build shared and sustainable access to high-quality data, tools and knowledge in the field of literary studies, in general, and Computational Literary Studies (CLS), in particular. To this end, a strong and balanced consortium of national knowledge and data infrastructures, high profile international projects and pan-European research infrastructures has been brought together. The project is led by the Institute of the Polish Language at the Polish Academy of Sciences.

DARIAH will be coordinating the transnational access activities and contribute to the outreach activities, the establishment of user-requirements and the provision of training and education for the CLS community through workshops, seminars, training schools and fellowships.

EOSC Future aims to deliver a fully functional platform of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by integrating data and resources from the science cluster communities in a technically mature and user-friendly framework through a co-design approach. To this end, the project will reinforce the EOSC-Core, which is the set of internal services allowing EOSC to operate and will expand the EOSC-Exchange, the set of federation services and resources provided by Research Infrastructures to serve the needs of the research communities. EOSC Future was granted 40,000,000 € for a period of two years and a half from April 2021.

EOSC Future is expected to extend the current EOSC model with the integration of a large amount of scientific resources and services under a common interoperable platform, by making them discoverable, accessible, and composable. DARIAH will be heavily involved in the integration of EOSC-Core services with resources provided by the research community.

Image by MetsikGarden from Pixabay

iii. A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

An Open Science Voice for the Humanities – a Humanities Voice for Open Science

What is the activity?

Fostering and implementing pathways to the open research culture as they specifically pertain to the arts and humanities research communities across and beyond the DARIAH network.

What kind of impact does it have?

The impact of these activities primarily manifest itself in changes in research culture; in changes in the EU research policy and it also enables the DARIAH member countries to collectively attract funding through European partnerships to address the gaps in the Open Science landscape together.

Who benefits?

DARIAH communities, humanities scholars, research support staff, science policy makers, Cultural Heritage professionals

Rationale for and Overview of the Activity

The digital transformation of research opened up radically new potentials in innovation and dissemination in all scientific areas. Open Science is becoming the new normal *modus operandi* in them, also as increasingly central conditions of research funding [1]. Still, in many cases, the dominant impact of STEM disciplines on the Open Science paradigm makes it uneasy for Arts and Humanities scholars to translate these values to their everyday research realities. Therefore, it is crucially important to establish a dedicated discourse and community practices around the open research culture as it makes sense in the arts and humanities disciplines. DARIAH is in a unique position to push forward to an open ecosystem that is organically growing out from real community practices and needs.

Description of the Impact

1. Policy Impact:

In the past couple of years, DARIAH has become a globally recognised representative of arts and humanities in the European science policy landscape and is member of key European policy bodies such as the Open Science Policy Platform or the [EOSC Training and Skills Working Group](#). DARIAH's contributions have been recognised, endorsed or taken up by high-level organisations like OSPP, OPERAS, EASSH, or ALLEA [2].

“The reason we selected DARIAH-EU to be on board was exactly because of the need of your voice in the OSPP. [...] I believe that all the big science challenges we have this century are multi disciplinary and thus need the Arts and humanities too. Finally, by having you there, we gave a strong signal that OS is as much a challenge as an opportunity for your peers than it is for any other scientific discipline.”

Jean-Claude Burgelman (Head of Unit Open Data Policies and Science Cloud DG RTD between 2017-2020; former chair of the Open Science Policy Platform)

Further, DARIAH's call for diversifying business models of Open Access publication in response to Plan S [3] has contributed to a significant policy change as the Coalition S is now exploring collaborative, non-commercial publishing models for Open Access that allow deviation from the pay-to-publish models [4]. DARIAH's statement also found strong resonance among arts and humanities scholars.

2. Cultural Impact

Since 2018, DARIAH has been actively supporting its communities in making their scholarly practices more open via training, workshops [5], infrastructural support, DARIAH's Open Access policy [6] and dedicated Open Science services such as the [DARIAH Open](#) blog, the [OpenMethods](#) platform or the [Open Science helpdesk](#).

Impact and reach of DARIAH's advocacy is evidenced by user statistics of relevant DARIAH resources: 18,211 unique visitors of DARIAH Open in its first year (January to December 2019) from around the globe. The [keynote lecture on Open Science](#) of the DARIAH Annual Event 2018 has been viewed more than 1,300 times. The preprint version of the book chapter [‘The risk of losing thick description: Data management challenges Arts and Humanities face in the evolving FAIR data ecosystem’](#) was downloaded more than 200 times within the first three months of its publication.

DARIAH's face to face events dedicated to Open Science attract a diverse and international audience and usually run full house. The demand for domain-specific Open Science advocacy is also reflected in the choice of the DESIR Cooperating partners. For the DESIR winter school, 20 participants received travel grants from DARIAH out of more than 70 applications from all over Europe.

“I liked the enthusiasm of the lecturers and their readiness to answer the questions of the participants. They tried their best to adapt their materials to our knowledge and background. I felt that the school had a very positive impact on all of us. I am definitely motivated to work further on my research and Phd studies. The organisers were very helpful and insightful too.”

Participants' evaluation of the DESIR Winter School

Another, more established community around open research practices in DARIAH forms the Editorial Team of the OpenMethods platform. They select, curate and review Open Access content about Digital Humanities tools and methods to increase the visibility and trust towards open solutions and gain peer recognition to them. The team is constantly growing, currently including 30 members who curate content in 14 languages [7].

3. [Attracting Funding through European Partnerships to Address the Gaps in the Open Science Landscape](#)

Thematic research infrastructures are critical for the future of Open Science as they build the infrastructural prerequisites of it and make sure that the emerging ecosystem is truly inclusive with all disciplines and geographical regions. Since 2017, DARIAH has been contributing to European projects with an explicit focus on Open Science.

Through these projects, we build bridges between local and domain-specific communities of practice and the emerging European Open Scholarship ecosystem. For instance, through our participation in the OpenAIRE project, we connected thematic data services from the national levels that are important for the Arts and Humanities communities to the European data commons [8, 9]. Having well-established information management and discovery systems in place, inclusive with all disciplines, is an absolute prerequisite of showcasing the value and richness of arts and humanities scholarship.

DARIAH will continue being responsive to the fast-changing policy landscape and bringing it closer to arts and humanities scholars' desks. In the coming period, our focus areas will support the meaningful realisation of FAIR data in the arts and humanities disciplines, including close collaborations between the Cultural Heritage sector [10].

Collage of translation and reflections on DARIAH Open posts

2. Connecting, Informing, Creating and Fostering

a. Measuring our Impact

The four pillars of DARIAH's strategy have come into clear focus as we have worked within the productive constraints of the first Strategic Action Plan over the past years while we launched a plan with a number of quantitative and qualitative KPIs, expressed in the form of a Balanced Scorecard covering the areas of Use, Efficiency, Scientific and Community Impact. Based on this work, that set the foundations of how to measure our impact, the aim in 2020 was to implement and enrich this plan with a set of numbers that would help us grasp how we add value as a research infrastructure.

Evaluating the success of an organisation is a crucial activity, defined also in terms of making progress toward its strategic goals. DARIAH has made great efforts to define a set of indicators that truly capture and measure success based upon a solid understanding of what our stakeholders value. What we really want our

KPIs to provide evidence for and focus our efforts upon is the depth and richness of our impact into research communities, into national consortia, into the practices and knowledge base of individual researchers who may or may not consider themselves 'digital humanists'.

In this spirit, in 2020 we collected indicators throughout the central European office and national consortia to populate the Balanced Scorecard while we produced our first three Impact Case Studies on Cooperations (see pages 20-21), Open Science (see pages 16-18) and the Working Group on Lexical Resources (see pages 12-13). Here, we would like to give a glimpse of the richness documented in numbers from our national consortia.

i. A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

Cooperating to Improve Research Capacity in Europe: DARIAH's Work in Cooperative Contexts

What is the activity?

DARIAH cooperates systematically and strategically with a wide range of partner institutions with the aim of delivering significant added benefits for its users and stakeholders in terms of the provision of access to tools, knowledge transfer and opportunities.

What kind of impact does it have?

Our wide network of goal-driven and carefully-chosen partnerships allows DARIAH to improve and support organisational efficiency, build human capital, target the needs of specific communities and enhance sustainability of resources. It also promotes innovation and the development of novel, shared tools, services and policy responses.

Who benefits?

DARIAH's research community, funders, staff and direct contributors; the community of research infrastructures and research policymakers.

Rationale for and Overview of the Activity

Cooperation is central to DARIAH's conceptualisation of both optimally efficient and scientifically useful infrastructure. Wider integration produces, in the long run, greater strength and coverage, but this integration has its limits, as the specific needs of a given community cannot always be met through broad spectrum development. The spectrum of cooperative efforts DARIAH engages in is therefore multifaceted: at one end of this range, we engage in largely bilateral relationships with key organisations, in particular other ERICs, often reflecting the rich interweavings of infrastructures in the national consortia that feed into DARIAH-EU. We also maintain small and larger group cooperative efforts as well as field-wide community participation on key macro-level issues.

Description of the Impact

The following three examples illustrate DARIAH's cooperative range:

1. Targeted Cooperation with CLARIN ERIC:

DARIAH's long standing programme of activities in cooperation with CLARIN [1, 2] is overseen by regular bilateral meetings of the two organisations' Directors. The two ERICs have launched specific cooperative ventures, from service launch and stabilisation to funding proposals, across fields of shared interest and activity,

including training, communications and policy ventures. Between us, the most mature output of our focussed cooperation is the [Digital Humanities Course Registry](#), originally an ad-hoc project of a DARIAH Working Group, now a well-maintained and active resource, funded and governed under a shared MOU between DARIAH and CLARIN.

The DH Course Registry website had 2424 visits from 78 countries in 2017 and 3607 visits from 90 countries in 2018. From January 2019 to May 2019 the website had 1911 visits from 103 countries.

"I found your website, the DH COURSE REGISTRY, not very long ago, and I think it's really a great job! I'm wondering if the manager or founder of this website would be interested in writing a report on digital humanities education based on these data? ... Since there are more and more DH programs in China recent years, scholars and librarians in China would be very interested in this kind of message and report."

Peng Xiao, Associate Research Fellow in Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China speaking about the DH Course Registry

2. The DARIAH Marketplace: Building (cooperatively) at Home, Sharing Abroad:

The longstanding vision of a DARIAH Marketplace for tools, services and data is finally being realised in cooperation with the full group of SSH ERICs via the SSH Open Cloud project, in particular the ‘First Tier’ meetings of all SSH ERIC Directors (plus LIBER and the SME Trust IT). This initiative has also been an opportunity to address an international infrastructure gap through links with the legacy [project Bamboo DiRT](#) (University of Berkeley and Stanford University, US) and active [project TAPoR](#) (University of Alberta, CA). International connections are of particular interest in some ways, so we do explore them actively (as via our ‘[DARIAH Beyond Europe](#)’ meetings of 2018-2019), but where we maintain a relatively high bar regarding further cooperation, recognising that the costs to deliver and maintain such connections can be particularly high.

The DARIAH Beyond Europe event series created three rare and precious opportunities for deep, strategic engagement between DARIAH and our counterparts in the US and Australia.

“This workshop is a great opportunity to engage ... Without an event like this we would be stuck on our own, devising our own modes and methods of sustainability in infrastructure.”

Glen Worthey, Digital Humanities Librarian in the Stanford University Libraries

“This event, and our collaboration with DARIAH, is really fundamental ... it’s really an exchange about opening up new avenues of enquiry for research.”

Joy Damoussi, President of the Australian Academy of the Humanities

3. Towards a Stronger RI Sector:

DARIAH contributed to the [RITrain](#) curriculum and training programme for research infrastructure managers, ensuring that the perspectives of non-science RIs were represented. It was also a founding signatory of the ERIC Forum in 2017. The RITrain Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures has produced two cohorts of qualified graduates, including DARIAH’s own Secretary General. A textbook featuring the curriculum is currently in press with Springer. DARIAH is also one of the founding members of the [ERIC Forum](#), of [EASSH](#) (the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities), and the [EOOSC Association](#), which will oversee the roll out phase of the ambitious European Open Science Cloud development.

To date DARIAH has featured in the curriculum of three cohorts of EMMRI students, and will be featured in the chapter on strategic planning in the forthcoming textbook.

“[DARIAH’s] participation is always inspiring for all participants [in the EMMRI programme], and I would really be happy to have you on board again.”

Eliabetta Marfotti, University of Milan Bicocca, Lecturer, EMMRI Masters Programme speaking about the DARIAH’s contribution to RI Train

DARIAH Annual Event 2018 @Encre Noire Corporate

b. Connecting Communities

i. Virtual Exchange Event

On May 28, at the initial dates of the DARIAH Annual Event, DARIAH organised a Virtual Exchange Event as a first reaction to the COVID 19 pandemic. The remit of this event was to run an event online that acted at a meta level - offering scholarly considerations of how digital humanists share knowledge while allowing the event itself to become a means of knowledge exchange.

The live event was held on May 28 while an online exhibition space was launched in the weeks leading up to the event that took the structure of a conference: a 'registration desk' that provided all the logistical and introductory information needed for the event; a 'knowledge exchange' area that hosted videos and blogs as well as links to news items, scholarly blogs and project websites that investigated and discussed scholarly practices; and a 'coffee break' area that included non-academic items such as a Spotify playlist, virtual city tours or a collection of remote working spaces. Each of these spaces on the website were designed to recreate the sense of space and place that comes from attending a conference, while also acknowledging the limitations of the virtual in this regard. Leading up to the event, the website numbered more than 400 visits from all over the world, with more than a thousand unique page views.

The live event itself, with 85 registered participants, was formatted to rely very heavily on the interactive element of conferences. It ran for two and a half hours, and any keynote or introductory presentations were limited to no

more than 20 minutes to prevent 'Zoom fatigue'. Instead, the majority of the sessions was based around breakout groups and short 3-minute presentations that were designed to prompt and encourage discussion.

ii. DARIAH Virtual Annual Event 2020

The **DARIAH Virtual Annual Event 2020** was different from any other DARIAH Annual Events. Initially scheduled to take place in May in Zagreb, Croatia, the event was postponed to the fall and transformed into an online conference as a result of the COVID 19 pandemic. The programme had to be completely planned anew and adapted to the online environment. In doing this, the Programme Committee drew from the experience and the recommendations of the Virtual Exchange Event, which took place a few months before.

Moving the event online to accommodate all the planned sessions called for creative solutions. In the end, after brainstorming with the Programme Committee and the DARIAH Coordination Office, it was decided to spread the workshops, synergy sessions and Working Group meetings into weekly sessions starting in October and ending in December. In addition, a conference “central” week (November 10 to 13) ensured enough time and visibility to the many papers and posters accepted from scholars from all over Europe. The result was a very rich event including 15 sessions of Working Group meetings, synergy sessions and workshops, 18 paper presentations, a poster exhibition with 18 posters and 1 demo, 1 keynote by John Unsworth and 2 social events.

More than 300 participants from 40 countries attended the online sessions to present research or exchange knowledge under the overall theme of the event, scholarly primitives. 2020 marked twenty years since John Unsworth first formulated his idea of scholarly primitives as a set of recursive and interrelated functions that form the foundations of research activities across disciplines. The DARIAH Annual Event was an opportunity to revisit the notion and scope of scholarly primitives in the context of the ongoing developments in the field of Digital Humanities and DARIAH's continuous efforts in shaping an effective and sustainable research infrastructure that meets the needs of humanities scholars.

A highlight of the event was the keynote given by John Unsworth himself, which revisited and interrogated both the notion and the scope of scholarly primitives twenty years later, and was followed by a lively discussion with the participants.

Photo by Chris Montgomery on Unsplash

iii. EURISE Network Online Series

The **EURISE Network** was launched as a common initiative of the three Social Sciences and Humanities ERICs, CESSDA, CLARIN and DARIAH, and joined by OPERAS in 2020, with the aim of creating a forum for research infrastructures to meet research software engineers. Over the last months of 2020, **four online expert meetings** gathered around 30 research software engineers to discuss and share good practices on technical challenges shared by distributed research infrastructures.

A first session on **Testing, Automation and Continuous Integration Workflows** was an opportunity to discuss the best ways to ensure software quality across research infrastructures. The second session focused on **Technical Documentation** as code, able to ease the generation, management and update of documentation. Sharing expertise on **Observability** was at the heart of the third session, during which the blurry line between observability and monitoring, the relationships between them, and concrete solutions and methods applied by the research infrastructures were examined. Finally, the **Infrastructure Provisioning** session allowed some exchange on new paradigms for state-of-the-art service provisioning, as well as the ways participants implemented service deployment in their environments.

DARIAH's presence and contribution to the EURISE network is key to ensuring the coherence of the SSH service offer in Europe and for DARIAH to develop a sustainable distributed infrastructure based on strong technical and procedural frameworks.

As stated by Tibor Kálmán (GWDG/ DARIAH representative in the EURISE network) "While general consensus reigns about the need to apply state-of-the-art software engineering principles and industry standards to the development and maintenance of software and services, the implementation proves hard. This is why we continue raising awareness inside our scholarly communities and giving advice on these issues for the policy makers of the SSH research infrastructures." And this is also the reason why EURISE will continue its work in 2021 to harmonise technical recommendations and processes in research software engineering (RSE).

c. DARIAH Funding Schemes

i. The DARIAH Theme 2020: 'Arts Exchanges' and 'Arts, Humanities and COVID 19'

Taking into consideration DARIAH's aim to explore and provide more support to the arts community within DARIAH, we decided to dedicate the 2020 DARIAH Theme Call to Arts. On the one hand, we had the intention to grow our understanding of the infrastructural requirements of this community with regards to the technologies they use. On the other hand, the impact of the COVID 19 pandemic and the ways that arts and humanities, and DARIAH by extension, can contribute to the response to this global challenge couldn't be more pertinent.

We therefore launched two streams of funding, '**Arts Exchanges**' and '**Arts, Humanities and COVID 19**', which attracted a high number of exciting proposals. After careful evaluation by the appointed Selection Committee, composed of members of the Board of Directors, the Scientific Board and the Joint Research Committee, nine projects were selected for funding with an overall budget of 87,920 €. The projects started at the end of the year and the results are expected to be presented at the DARIAH Annual Event 2022 in Athens, Greece.

Winning Projects

DARIAH Arts Exchanges

1. Empty Mind, Ine Vanoveren, Kristof Timmerman (DARIAH-BE)

This project aims to make contemporary (performing) art(s) accessible for an audience that normally is being excluded from a cultural and artistic experience, because of physical, geographic and/or economical disadvantages. Through artistic research, the project team will investigate new creative possibilities – lacunae that became apparent because of the drastic change in their cultural and artistic experience.

2. Folk music groups: their artistic practice and infrastructural needs in the COVID 19 era and beyond, Magdalena Chudy, Ewa Łukasik, Ewa Kuśmierk, Tomasz Parkoła (DARIAH-PL)

This project aims to identify and understand infrastructural requirements of folk music artists with regard to the technologies they use through user needs assessment exercises and engagements. The feedback gathered from artists based on these exercises will be analysed in order to draw conclusions intended to guide the development of technological solutions offered to this community.

3. International Evening Class, Annett Busch (Norwegian University of Science and Technology)

International Evening Class combines old and new ways of working and learning together, in synchronised asynchronous modes. The project team envisions a multi-local and virtual structure operating in-between, connecting various educational and cultural institutions, to create and display hybrid forms of research and knowledge.

Arts, Humanities and COVID 19

1. Contemporary collecting and COVID 19: barriers, bottlenecks, and perspectives in digital curation, Chiara Zuanni (DARIAH-AT)

This project aims to map current barriers and potential solutions in collecting, curating, preserving, and interpreting objects and memories of the COVID 19 pandemic by fostering an interdisciplinary discussion around the challenges of contemporary collecting in memory institutions, as well as to test potential solutions for the collection, management, preservation, and dissemination of collections related to COVID 19, in collaboration with a range of cultural stakeholders.

2. DH in Transition: A mixed approach and a hybrid publication on the effects of COVID 19 in DH research and practice, Maria Ilvanidou, Agjatis Benardou (DARIAH-GR)

This project aims to design and organise a digital workshop in which the project team will reunite the Twitter Conference participants ('DH in the time of virus', April 2020) alongside further DH researchers who will be selected through an open call to revisit, reappraise and reevaluate considerations, remarks, and research outputs presented in April 2020.

3. Electronic Literature (e-lit) and COVID 19, Soeren Pold (DARIAH-DK)

How is the COVID 19 pandemic, resulting measures, and movement of cultural life online reflected in electronic literature and other digital narrative practices online? This project aims to develop an analytical research study, an open-access research collection, an online exhibition and a critical study of electronic literature and digital art produced during this time of COVID 19.

4. Fitting inside COVID 19. Aesthetic Resilience of Contemporary Music facing a Pandemic Crisis, Marlies De Munck (DARIAH-BE)

In this collaboratively produced research, an interdisciplinary research team consisting of two musicians, a philosopher of music and a sociologist of art, will study the impact of COVID 19 on the aesthetic resilience of artistic production within the contemporary music sector.

5. Making the Pandemic Understandable Using Public, Hi-resolution Screens, Eveline Wandl-Vogt (Ars Electronica Linz GmbH & Co KG)

The project team aims to make visible the massive scientific work that doctors, researchers, and academics are doing to fight the illness provoked by COVID 19, by making use of data visualisation in public spaces to foster not only the understanding but also the conversation among viewers.

6. Visualising the Virus, Sria Chatterjee (IXDM, FHNW, Basel & Max-Planck Kunsthistorisches Institut)

This project connects the artistic, scientific and the political through a multi-faceted and participatory study of the ways the coronavirus is visualised. The overall aim of the project is to create an online platform that serves as a repository of images and ideas that allow visitors to make the connections between art, science and politics in the context of COVID 19.

Photo by Steve Johnson on Unsplash

ii. Outcomes of the Working Groups Funding Scheme 2019

In 2019, DARIAH launched its second Working Groups Funding Scheme, funding five projects for one year (November 2019 – November 2020) with an overall budget of 24,862 €. The pandemic, however, affected most of the projects and some of them had to be extended. Two projects managed to be completed on time, featured below, and their results are a milestone for DARIAH, providing two very important services in the DARIAH landscape.

1. ELDAH Consent Form:

Since the coming into effect of the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR), humanities researchers have been unsure about how to do certain parts of their research while considering their subjects' right to privacy. The DARIAH Working Group ELDAH decided to fill this gap by developing the [Consent Form Wizard](#) (CFW).

This tool enables researchers to correctly approach the management of personal data in compliance with the GDPR. After responding to a series of questions, researchers receive a standardised GDPR-compliant form for obtaining consent from data subjects in DH projects (e.g. from visitors of scientific events, survey participants, etc). The resulting consent forms are valid throughout the entire European Union and will therefore serve the entire DARIAH and DH community. The project was jointly developed and funded by [CLARIAH-AT](#), [DARIAH-EU](#) and [DARIAH-HR](#) and supported by SSHOC.

2. DH Course Registry Communication and Dissemination Plan:

The [DH Course Registry](#) (DHCR) is a search environment that allows users to access a database containing, at this point, over 230 courses and training events in Europe and beyond. This funded project developed a strategy to benefit from the already existing communication networks (DARIAH, CLARIN) in a planned way to increase the reach of the DH Course Registry and the impact of the Working Group. At a technical level, the funding allowed for interface updates and user experience improvements on the Working Group's website.

d. Creating Tools and Services for the Community

i. The SSH Open Marketplace in 2020: From Alpha to Beta

The SSH Open Marketplace is one of the major outputs of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project. Two versions of this discovery portal for SSH resources were released in 2020: an alpha version opened for testers in June and a beta version available for public testing in December, accessible at marketplace.sshopencloud.eu. Featuring more than 5 000 items from five different resource genres (Tools & Services, Training Materials, Datasets, Publications and Workflows), the beta version of the SSH Open Marketplace is the result of work led by DARIAH-EU involving DARIAH partner institutions, such as ACDH-CH, PSNC, UGOE or CNRS, but also partner infrastructures like CLARIN and CESSDA with whom a shared governance model is foreseen to sustain the service after the end of the project.

Collective efforts to enrich and curate the data populating the SSH Open Marketplace are on the agenda for 2021, but users can already explore the collection – e.g. by browsing through the content along concepts of the newly released version 2 of the TaDiRAH taxonomy – and discover how relations between services and training materials or between tools and publications are highlighted in the user-centric interface.

ii. OpenAIRE-DARIAH Research Community Gateway

In parallel to establishing a more systematic approach to DARIAH's services, in 2020 we continued to improve the connectivity of key DARIAH-affiliated services and digital scholarly outputs to the European research discovery landscape within the framework of the OpenAIRE Advance Project.

The [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#) and [OpenAIRE Explore](#), a portal that is built on top of the graph, is one of the largest publicly owned scholarly discovery services in Europe that is inclusive with a wide range of content types. It is expected to become a central service within the EOSC. The OpenAIRE Advance project enabled DARIAH to connect and increase the profile of arts and humanities research in this environment through a dedicated [DARIAH Research Community Gateway](#) that was publicly released in October 2020.

The Gateway is a single entry point to DARIAH-affiliated research outputs, such as publications, TEI encoded digital critical editions and data. As a result, content types that are important for the arts and humanities communities became visible in the DARIAH Gateway but also became part of the OpenAIRE Research Graph and the OpenAIRE [Digital Humanities and Cultural heritage collection](#) to increase their visibility and reusability beyond geographical, language and disciplinary borders.

e. Training Initiatives

DARIAH-Campus: Further Development

DARIAH-Campus was launched as an output of the DESIR project in December 2019. Throughout 2020, new training materials were added to the suite of resources that included live-captured events from DARIAH Members and affiliated bodies. As 2020 became a year of online learning due to the COVID 19 pandemic, visits to the Campus site bore out this trend. April 2020 had the highest number of visits to the site, with almost twice as many separate visits than in any other recorded month in 2020, as Europe-wide people went into lockdown.

DARIAH-Campus saw a spike in visitors in late March and April, which indicates a response to the global pandemic, and a need among users to seek online training resources in order to teach remotely. Analysis of these statistics in comparison to the PARTHENOS Training Suite shows a similar pattern, particularly when compared with the PARTHENOS TS's site statistics in previous years in which the same spike is not present.

The DARIAH-Campus site itself is managed using GitHub, thus enabling content providers to maintain control over the input of their resources. During 2020, additional resources designed to help the user were published on DARIAH-Campus, including the DARIAH Reuse Charter. A citation format was also added to each page that credits the course content authors and providers. Learning Outcomes were also added as part of the template for resources that are locally hosted directly on the DARIAH-Campus site, and while they are not a requirement for externally hosted resources, they are encouraged. This assists users to determine how a resource can further their skills development.

Through collaboration with course providers throughout the year, and by discussing their experience of using GitHub for adding these materials, the DARIAH-Campus team has begun looking at ways to make the process of uploading course content uploading easier. As a result, in 2021 it is planned that a new content management system will be available alongside Github, to help course providers to upload their modules and training materials with greater ease.

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Launch of Training Tuesday

The #TrainingTuesday Twitter campaign was launched in January 2020 to draw our audience to digital humanities resources developed by partners and affiliated projects of the DARIAH infrastructure. More than 45 training resources on digital humanities were highlighted on Tuesdays throughout 2020, in an effort to showcase the richness of available material hosted on various DARIAH and DARIAH-affiliated platforms.

This campaign has received a warm welcome in its first year. Statistics drawn from Twitter showed that the most engagements with the campaign occurred in April and May, with a total of 630 interactions on Twitter in those two months. In September 2020, LIBER expressed the interest to join the #TrainingTuesday campaign to showcase their training materials and a cooperative collaboration was agreed to enhance virtual traffic to one another's training resources.

The #TrainingTuesday campaign continues in 2021, and hopes to expand to include resources from the wider DARIAH community.

Launch of Friday Frontiers

As part of DARIAH's commitment to establishing itself as a learning organisation, DARIAH launched its In-House Webinar series in Autumn 2020. The first programme of events was called the Friday Frontiers, with one-hour webinars running from October to December. Three webinars that were held in this time brought researchers from the wider DARIAH community in touch with experts in different pan-disciplinary topics: post-publication peer review, the Time-Machine Project, and flipped classrooms.

The aim of these webinars is to foster a culture of continuous learning and upskilling among DARIAH's various bodies and members. The presentations themselves were recorded and are available on DARIAH-Campus as a learning resource.

3. Doing Things Right and Doing the Right Things

a. Changes in the organisation

While 2020 has been a year of global turmoil, it has been very stable among the DARIAH core staff, which helped us to overcome the challenges of the pandemic. In 2020, neither the DARIAH Coordination Office nor the Board of Directors saw any changes in their composition. However, two figures within DARIAH who have shared the journey since the very beginning ended their terms of office in November 2020 after 6 years of valuable guidance and expertise: Jacques Dubucs, Chair of the General Assembly and Riccardo Pozzo, Chair of the Scientific Board.

The Scientific Board was largely renewed in 2020. In addition to the departure of Riccardo Pozzo, Jan Rybicki, Jane Ohlmeyer and Francis Prost stepped down from the board. At the same time, three new members were appointed: Andrea Rapp, Andrew Perkis and Panos Constantopoulos joined in May 2020. Each of these excellent additions contributes to the disciplinary, regional and gender balance we seek to maintain on the Board. Last but not least, Patrick Svensson was elected Chair of the board.

Chris De Loof was elected as the new Chair of the General Assembly. Chris has been part of DARIAH ERIC since its establishment as National Representative of Belgium.

b. Policy developments

i. Progress on the Second Strategic Action Plan

The DARIAH Strategic Plan 2019-2026 focuses on four areas of activity, as shown in the graph below, around which we plan our activity over the period of the plan. In order to achieve the goals outlined in the Strategic Plan, DARIAH regularly renews its Strategic Action Plan (STRAPL), a supplementary document that captures our specific organisational goals within a shorter time horizon.

Within DARIAH's second STRAPL (2019-2022), we refined our concept of how to best create actions, framing them around clear challenges, teams to address them, time horizons for progress and clear assessment methodology. With 16 actions and a clear alignment to the Strategic Plan, the DARIAH team got busy in 2020 progressing on the planned actions.

In 2020, we found we were slightly more than halfway through the time period of the second such STRAPL (2019-2022). In spite of this early point in the lifetime of the STRAPL II, we had managed by the end of 2022 to progress our 16 objectives to a state of 72% completion. For example, significant progress has been noted in the services task force with a large series of internal consultations with DARIAH governance bodies that already took place within the year and a white paper produced to understand and guide services development within the DARIAH infrastructure (see next section for

more about this). In addition, the project related to the construction of the discovery platform for tools and services in the arts and humanities – the SSH Open Marketplace – continues to progress well. A brand new policy for the Cooperating Partners has been developed to strengthen the links with DARIAH central and increase the joint outputs of the partnerships. DARIAH also progressed in the Training and Education pillar tasks, by becoming a learning organisation, organising in-house training sessions called Friday Frontiers.

Progress to date on the DARIAH Second Strategic Action Plan (as of 31 December 2020)

Major achievements in 2020: Development of a new policy for the Cooperating Partners; DARIAH became a learning organisation with in-house training sessions (called Friday Frontiers). Service portfolio and marketplace further developed.

ii. Towards a DARIAH Services Policy

2020 was a rich year for exploring DARIAH’s approach to services. The main strategic question discussed in a series of meetings and consultations with all DARIAH bodies was: **to what extent should DARIAH seek to become better known as a provider of Europe-wide technical services?**

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) context and its XaaS (everything-as-a-service) approach drives Research Infrastructures towards the clarification of their services offer. Based on the diversity of services declared as DARIAH in-kind contributions by the national members, and the services developed within projects or via the Working Groups, DARIAH has a long-standing experience of the arts and humanities research services needs, development and best practices. Nevertheless the coherence of the service offer in a distributed infrastructure does not go without challenges.

In the White Paper ‘Towards a concise DARIAH service strategy’ an assessment of the current situation was carried out and scenarios to implement an efficient service management were developed. The different consultations that followed with the National Coordinators, the General Assembly and the Scientific Board have provided valuable feedback and showed strong support for a better structure and visibility of DARIAH’s services at the European level. While 2020 has laid the groundwork for the reshaping of DARIAH’s service offer, 2021 will be the year of concrete actions: design of a service management workflow, development of a structure portfolio, a better alignment between DARIAH service offer and the in-kind contributions as well as a better communication and dissemination of the service catalogue.

Some examples of DARIAH services:

DIGITAL HUMANITIES COURSE REGISTRY

jointly powered by DARIAH and CLARIN

developed within the ELDAH Working Group

Vocabs

Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities, updated within CLARIAH-DE and hosted on the Vocabs repository, a DARIAH service powered by DARIAH-AT

developed within the former HaS project and sustained by DARIAH-EU

provided by DARIAH-DE

iii. DARIAH's position paper on Cultural Heritage Data from a Humanities Perspective

The COVID 19 pandemic and losing physical access to Cultural Heritage Institutions made even more apparent how much arts and humanities research depends on the digital availability of artefacts of our collective cultural memory. In response to the immediate challenges coming with the rapid switch to virtual/online-only workflows, we found it timely and crucial to call attention to some long standing, key barriers to the development of digital research methods (such as IPR complexities, restrictions of text and data mining or the varying quality of digitisation) and address gaps in the relationship between cultural data and research data.

In the [Cultural Heritage Data from a Humanities Research Perspective](#) position paper, published in October 2020, we articulated a critical reflection on Europe's digitisation agenda, through the lens of arts and humanities research. This position paper was submitted to the European Commission as part of the EC's evaluation of the 2021 Recommendation on Digitisation and Online Accessibility of Cultural Material and Digital Preservation (REC 2011/711/EU).

A major barrier to overcome is that cultural heritage and research are traditionally seen as two separate sectors. As a result, in current research practices, knowledge creation between Cultural Heritage Institutions, Digital Humanities centres and researchers is separated by institutional and infrastructural silos. A key argument of the position paper is that FAIR data can only become a reality in arts and humanities if we could enable all the relevant actors to work together and establish mechanisms for improving the use and re-use of cultural heritage resources by researchers. This does not only

include rethinking digitisation strategies in terms of breadth, diversity and quantity, but also concerns and priorities regarding the quality of digitised material. The latter is crucial in enabling the advanced use of computational Digital Humanities methods.

The paper was written in alignment with ongoing work around the [Cultural Heritage Data Reuse Charter](#).

c. Strategy Days 2020

The DARIAH core bodies (Board of Directors, Senior Management Team, Heads of VCCs and the Coordination Office) started the year with the Strategy Days meeting, which was held at the offices of the DARIAH Coordination Team in Berlin, on January 20-22. The three days of work and exchange were an opportunity for the members of the various governing bodies to draft, discuss and develop the main strategic outlines of DARIAH ERIC for the year to come.

The agenda of the 2020 Strategy Days was busy with reviewing the progress on strategic tasks set out in the previous year, freshly interrogating the role of services in DARIAH, discussing and receiving expertise on the importance of lobbying for the arts and humanities and exploring the role of DARIAH in sustaining research outputs. The discussions and conclusions from the Strategy Days led to the creation of task forces with set objectives to reach within the year, for example in re-evaluating the role of Cooperating Partners within DARIAH, considering DARIAH's position beyond Europe and the kinds of non-European collaborations that could be pursued and monitoring further work and progress in terms of STRAPL II.

4. Looking Ahead

As we assemble this report in the Spring of 2021, the world doesn't look quite as different now from how it did a year ago as we might have hoped. In spite of the unprecedented speed of the development and rollout of vaccines to combat the COVID 19 virus, many of us are still working from our spare rooms and bedrooms; many are still living under lockdowns and curfews; many have been ill, or lost loved ones. For DARIAH, this means that the outlook for 2021 will not bring us back to the kinds of rich, face-to-face interactions that are the foundation of knowledge exchange, but will continue to challenge us to be creative, responsive and resilient.

This does not mean that we do not have many exciting and innovative exchanges to look forward to, however. Our DARIAH Theme projects exploring the arts and COVID represent a significant body of work in a truly exciting space, and their results have the potential to stand as significant evidence of the contribution of the DARIAH disciplines in a global crisis. Similarly, the launch of our

Open Access monograph scheme in 2021 will allow us to increase access to this kind of scholarly visibility, and demonstrate the value of ensuring humanists have the same access to OA as do their STEM colleagues.

As an organisation, DARIAH is continuing to move forward, developing ambitious plans for improving the baseline for research in the arts and humanities, and expanding our points of connection outside of our consortium. While our Annual Event in 2021 will regrettably be delivered for a second year via the impoverished channels of online interaction, the DARIAH infrastructure moves forward, just as research does. We remain confident that we will emerge stronger and more creative for the deprivations we have endured: in the meantime, we will do all we can to achieve our mission as a research infrastructure for all of our disciplines and all modes of engagement.

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Appendix I: Administrative and Legal Details

Organisational chart

Who's who in DARIAH

Body: Board of Directors

	Jennifer Edmond	Trinity College Dublin
	Frank Fischer	Higher School of Economics, Moscow
	Toma Tasovac	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities

Body: Scientific Board (as of 31st December 2020)

Patrik Svensson	Chair of the DARIAH Scientific Board, UCLA
Arianna Betti	University of Amsterdam
Panos Constantopoulos	Athens University of Economics and Business
Chad Gaffield	University of Ottawa
Sarah Kenderdine	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Andrew Perkis	NTNU ARTEC
Andrea Rapp	Technical University Darmstadt
Roxane Wyns	LIBIS
Riccardo Pozzo	(Chair of the DARIAH Scientific Board until November 2020), Università di Verona
Jane Ohlmeyer	Trinity College Dublin
Jan Rybicki	Jagiellonian University

Body: Joint Research Committee

Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer	DARIAH/DANS
Adeline Joffres	JRC Member	TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS)
Tibor Kálmán	Heads of VCC1	GWDG
Matej Durco		ACDH-CH
Agiatis Benardou	Heads of VCC2	Digital Curation Unit, ATHENA R.C.
Marianne Ping Huang		Aarhus University
Georgios Artopoulos	Heads of VCC3	STARC, Cyprus Institute
Tomasz Parkola		Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
Fabio Cotti	Heads of VCC4	University of Roma Tor Vergata
Dirk Wintergrün		Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

Body: DARIAH Coordination Office

Arnaud Roi

Secretary General

Anne Grésillon

Administrative and Legal Officer

Marco Raciti

European Project Manager

Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra

Open Science Officer

Yoann Moranville

Developer and Research Associate

Laure Barbot

European Project Officer

Eliza Papaki

Outreach and Communications Officer

Vicky Garnett

Training and Education Officer

Andrea Scharnhorst

Chief Integration Officer

Francesca Morselli

Integration Officer

Femmy Admiraal

Integration Officer

Body: National Coordinators Committee		
Sally Chambers	Chair of NCC/Belgium	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities
Nicolas Larousse	Vice Chair of NCC/France	Huma Num
Mörth Karlheinz	Austria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, Austrian Academy of Sciences
Walter Scholger	Austria	Center for Information Modeling – Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, University of Graz
Dimitar Iliev	Bulgaria	Sofia University
Kiril Simov	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar	Croatia	Archive, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Martin Lhoták	Czech Republic	Czech Academy of Sciences
Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard	Denmark	Digital Humanities Lab Denmark
Nanette Reißler-Pipka	Germany	Göttingen State and University Library
Paris Potiropoulos	Greece	Academy of Athens
Orla Murphy	Ireland	University College Cork
Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Italy	Italian Council of Research
Andreas Fickers	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Richard Zijdeman	Netherlands	International Institute of Social History (IISH)
Jakub Szprot	Poland	ICM, University of Warsaw
Amelia Aguiar Andrade	Portugal	NOVA FCSH
Snežana Petrović	Serbia	Serbian Academy for Sciences and Arts
Jurij Hadalin	Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History/Primorska University

Appendix II: Finances

1) DARIAH ERIC

a) Financial overview

In 2020, 19 member countries contributed to DARIAH ERIC's budget in two different ways: through cash and in-kind contributions. In 2020, according to the budget voted by the General Assembly, the contributions from the member countries amounted to:

2020 total cash contribution	737,010 €
2020 total in-kind contribution	4,424,813 €

It should be noted that the financial information in this Annual Report 2020 has not been audited yet. The General Assembly, responsible for validating the accounts of the fiscal year 2020, will indeed only meet in November 2021. It should be mentioned, nonetheless, that the last report of the auditor about the year 2019 concluded that DARIAH's financial statements "give a true and fair view of the assets and liabilities and of the financial position and of the net assets of its operation according to the French accounting principles".

Despite that, DARIAH is able to give an accurate situation of its finances that reflect DARIAH's operations in an understandable and transparent manner for its stakeholders.

It is important to clarify that in this first section, only the resources and expenses of DARIAH – without European and other projects – are accounted for. Due to their very nature, the in-kind contributions are not included in the calculation of resources available to run DARIAH's operations. The total income 2020 is mostly composed of cash contributions and overheads of European projects that have been completed, as well as some reimbursements, e.g. due to cancelled travels. As a result, the financial overview for the year 2020 is as follows:

<i>Balance previous year</i>	562,153 €
Income 2020	868,651 €
Expenses 2020	740,906 €
Balance 2020	127,746 €
Total balance	689,898 €

b) Focus on the expenses

The largest component of operating expenses is by far the personnel costs which represent 80% of the total costs. Support to the research communities follows with 12% and refers to tailored project funding for scholars in the arts and humanities. The operational costs for the year 2020 are distributed as follows:

Type of costs – DARIAH only	2020
Personnel costs	595,896 €
Community support through project funding	87,609 €
Accounting & audit	20,100 €
Travel & accomodation	10,979 €
Consulting	10,747 €
Communication	9,529 €
Consumables	2,358 €
Catering	2,191 €
Bank charges	1,431 €
Training	65 €
Total	740,906 €

c) Focus on personnel costs

Personnel costs are the largest item of expenditure which reflects a strong and diverse team that works directly to support the research communities and meet their needs in terms of communication, research policy, service development, etc. It should be noted that the above-mentioned personnel costs do not take into account the work carried out in the framework of the European projects and represent only 73% of the total labour costs. Next is the composition of the DARIAH central team:

Personnel Costs – administration	FTE
Directors	1,5
Secretary-General	1
Legal and administration officer	1
European project manager	0,4

Personnel Costs – support for the community	FTE
Communication officer	1
Developer/technical support	1
EU Project manager (SSHOC project)	1
Training and education officer	0,6
Open Science officer	1
Working Group coordinators and experts for in-kind contributions	0,8

2) European projects

a) Financial overview

European project funding is solely used to carry out specific projects in which DARIAH is a partner, including:

- DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined (DESIR), Grant agreement number 731081. The project ended on 31.12.2019. However, few expenses have been made at the beginning of 2020 such as audit or personnel costs to wrap up the projects.
- OpenAIRE Advancing Open Scholarship (OpenAIRE Advance), Grant agreement number 777541.
- The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase (E-RIHS PP), Grant agreement number 739503.
- The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC), Grant agreement number 823782.
- The ERIC Forum Implementation project (ERIC Forum), Grant agreement number 823798.
- Preparing open access in the European research area through scholarly communication (OPERAS-P), Grant agreement number 871069.
- Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration (TRIPLE), Grant agreement number 863420.

The table below includes personnel as well as other direct costs, such as travel expenses or events organisation:

	Credit	Debit
DESIR	24,977 €	24,977 €
SSHOC	66,590 €	66,590 €
TRIPLE	30,046 €	30,046 €
OPERAS P	84,523 €	84,523 €
OpenAIRE Advance	18,299 €	18,299 €
ERIC Forum	695 €	695 €
E-RIHS PP	7,423 €	7,423 €
Total European projects	232,552 €	232,552 €

b) Focus on the expenses

Type of costs – EU projects	2020
Staff costs	215,383 €
Travel & accomodation	11,862 €
Accounting & audit	3,600 €
Consumables	1,707 €
Total	232,552 €

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